

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE FOR CHEMISTRY STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract

As the global scientific community becomes more interconnected, proficiency in foreign languages, particularly English, is critical for chemistry students. This paper examines the role of foreign language learning in facilitating global scientific communication, enhancing career opportunities, and fostering intercultural competence among chemistry students. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, including a literature review and surveys, this study explores the benefits and challenges of integrating foreign language education into the chemistry curriculum. The findings underscore the need for language proficiency in international academic environments, providing recommendations for education systems to support language learning among non-linguist professionals.

Keywords: foreign language education, chemistry students, global communication, career opportunities, intercultural competence

Introduction

In today's globalized world, the role of foreign languages, particularly English, has grown significantly in scientific fields, including chemistry. English has established itself as the lingua franca of science, used extensively in academic publications, international conferences, and research collaborations (Tardy, 2004). As a result, students pursuing degrees in the hard sciences, such as chemistry, must acquire foreign language skills to effectively communicate their work, broaden their career prospects, and participate in global scientific endeavors.

The increasing demand for professionals who are proficient in both their technical field and a foreign language reflects a broader trend in higher education, which prioritizes interdisciplinary competence. However, foreign language learning is often neglected in non-linguistic disciplines. This paper aims to address the growing need for integrating foreign languages into the education of chemistry students and emphasizes the implications of this integration for career advancement and international collaboration.

Foreign language proficiency, particularly English, is essential for participating in the global scientific community. English-language scientific journals, international conferences, and collaborative research projects dominate the field of chemistry (Tardy, 2004). As Tardy (2004) notes, effective communication in English enables chemists to publish their research in high-impact journals and to collaborate across borders, which in turn drives scientific innovation.

Recent studies discuss the importance of combining language learning and science education, emphasizing that English language learners (ELLs) benefit from integrated instruction that enhances both their language skills and scientific understanding (Lee & Buxton, 2013).

Language skills not only enhance academic collaboration but also improve career prospects. Chemistry graduates with proficiency in foreign languages are more likely to secure positions in international companies, research institutes, and multinational corporations

Employers increasingly value candidates who can communicate with diverse teams, navigate cross-cultural settings, and engage in complex negotiations in multiple languages (Garcia, 2010; Kramsch, 2014).

Being fluent in more than one language can really open doors in the professional world. For instance, it can be seen that someone who can speak in a foreign language are able to secure a role at a multinational companies because of their ability to work across different regions and communicate with diverse teams. This isn't unusual—bilingual or multilingual professionals often find it easier to get jobs at international companies and research institutes. They even tend to earn more than their monolingual peers; some industries report salary increases of 1.5% to 10% (Berlitz, n.d.; Language Testing International, 2019). This kind of advantage is especially true in fields like healthcare and technology, where navigating cross-cultural situations and handling complex negotiations are part of the job (College News, 2021). In our interconnected world, language skills have become more than just a bonus—they're essential for those looking to work globally or participate in international research projects.

Beyond practical benefits, foreign language learning fosters intercultural competence, a crucial skill for working in today's interconnected scientific community. Intercultural competence involves understanding and respecting cultural differences, which are vital when collaborating with international colleagues or presenting research in diverse settings (Deardorff, 2006).

Byram (2008) emphasizes that intercultural competence helps scientists navigate the complexities of cross-cultural communication, facilitating more effective teamwork and problem-solving. For chemistry students, acquiring foreign languages is not merely a matter of linguistic proficiency; it also involves developing the ability to work harmoniously with peers from different cultural backgrounds, ultimately contributing to more successful and inclusive research outcomes.

Methods

This study employs a **mixed-methods approach**, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods.

This approach helps explore the relationship between foreign language learning and the professional development of chemistry students. The study is divided into the following phases:

1. Literature Review. The research began with a **comprehensive literature review**. In this phase, scientific articles, books, and reports related to chemistry education and foreign language learning were reviewed. The following approach was used to select relevant literature:

Databases: The study utilized well-known academic databases such as Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Web of Science. These platforms are recognized for their comprehensive scientific resources.

Search Keywords: To identify relevant articles, the following keywords were used: 'Foreign language learning', 'Chemistry education', 'Scientific communication', 'Cultural competence'.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Only studies published in the past 20 years were considered, ensuring the inclusion of the most up-to-date and relevant information. The focus was on research related to foreign language teaching to chemistry or STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields, with less emphasis on general language learning and teaching researches.

Analysis: The literature review highlighted key topics such as the role of foreign languages in international scientific communication, challenges faced by STEM students in language learning, and the need for integrating foreign languages into academic programs, including increasing the number of language courses or class hours.

2. Survey. A **mixed-methods survey** was conducted among chemistry students to explore their experiences with foreign language learning and its impact on their academic and professional development. The survey included the following types of questions:

Closed-Ended Questions: These questions aimed to collect quantitative data. Participants were asked about their proficiency in reading, writing, and speaking foreign languages, the importance of foreign languages for their professional future, and the availability of language learning opportunities in their academic programs.

Open-Ended Questions: Participants were encouraged to elaborate on their experiences, the challenges they faced, and suggestions for improving the integration of foreign language learning into chemistry education.

Survey Distribution: The survey was distributed online via Google Forms and face-to-face at universities. The online method allowed students to complete the survey at their convenience, while face-to-face surveys provided more detailed data on students' language proficiency levels.

Sample Selection: The survey involved **300 participants**, all chemistry students enrolled in bachelor's programs (1st to 4th year) of universities (Fargona state university, Andijan state university, Qo'qon state pedagogical institute). Of those, **85%** responded to the survey.

Survey Topics: The survey covered the following key topics:

- **Current proficiency in foreign languages:** Students assessed their current language learning levels.

- **Professional importance of foreign languages:** Students explained how important they think foreign languages, particularly English, are for their professional and academic activities.

- **Opportunities for foreign language learning in their education program:** Students provided feedback on the availability of foreign language learning opportunities in their university programs.

- **Challenges faced in foreign language learning:** Students described the difficulties they encountered in learning foreign languages.

3. Data Collection. Data from the survey were collected both **online** and **offline**. The data collection process involved the following steps:

- The survey was distributed using Google Forms or directly through faculty representatives to students participating in foreign language classes. Both methods were convenient and accessible for the students.

- Prior to participation, all participants provided informed consent. This document informed them of the study's purpose, safety measures, and their rights.

- Participants' responses were kept confidential, and no personal information was collected. The data were used solely for research purposes and stored securely.

4. Data Analysis. The survey results were analyzed using two main methods: **quantitative** and **qualitative analysis**.

Quantitative Analysis: Data from the closed-ended questions were analyzed using statistical software such as **SPSS** or **R**. This analysis helped clarify how students evaluate their language proficiency and the professional importance of foreign languages.

Qualitative Analysis: Responses to the open-ended questions were analyzed thematically. Key themes were identified to explore the challenges students face in language learning and how foreign language proficiency impacts their academic and professional success.

5. Ethical Considerations. The study adhered to strict **ethical guidelines** throughout the research process:

- Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the survey began, ensuring they understood their rights and the purpose of the research.

- Participants' responses remained anonymous and confidential.

- All collected data were securely stored in password-protected files, ensuring the protection of participants' privacy.

Results

The findings from the literature review and survey responses highlight the significant role of foreign languages, particularly English, in the academic and professional development of chemistry students. Survey results indicate that 90% of respondents recognize the

importance of English for accessing scientific publications and attending international conferences. However, only 40% feel adequately prepared to use English in professional settings.

The data also reveal a gap between students' language proficiency and the demands of the global scientific community. Many students reported limited opportunities for language learning within their academic programs, a trend that mirrors the findings of Richards (2017), who notes that foreign language education is often under-emphasized in science curricula.

Discussion

To address these challenges, educational institutions should consider several strategies to promote foreign language learning among chemistry students:

- Interdisciplinary Programs: Implement interdisciplinary courses that combine chemistry and language education, focusing on scientific terminology and communication strategies.

- Language for Specific Purposes (LSP): Develop specialized language courses designed for chemists, including English for scientific purposes.

- Study Abroad Programs: Encourage students to participate in exchange programs or internships abroad to immerse them in an English-speaking environment.

- Collaborative Projects: Foster international collaborations that require students to engage with peers from other countries, thereby reinforcing both language skills and intercultural competence.

Foreign language proficiency, particularly in English, is a key asset for chemistry students in today's globalized world. The ability to communicate across linguistic and cultural boundaries enhances students' career opportunities, facilitates international research collaborations, and fosters intercultural competence. As the scientific community continues to expand globally, educational institutions must prioritize foreign

language education for non-linguist professionals, ensuring that future chemists are well-equipped to navigate the complexities of a multilingual world.

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